
Important Aspects of Preparing Children for School Education

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Abstract: Preparing children for school education has its own criteria. In this process, preparing children for school physically, intellectually, mentally, willfully and spiritually is one of the bases that ensure their lack of stress in school education, continuity and effectiveness of education. The article covered the important aspects of comprehensive development of children in preschool education and preparation of children for school education.

Keywords: preschool education, school preparation, pedagogy, child psychology, spiritual development, physical development.

Introduction

Extensive reforms are being implemented in the field of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The constitutional rights of every citizen to education are implemented through the educational system introduced in the republic, its types and forms. Developments in the scientific field are widely supported by our state. Especially in this place, it is important to raise the young generation from a young age to become healthy and mature in all aspects, to introduce effective forms and methods of education into the educational process, and thereby to develop children.

Article 8 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education":

- Pre-school education and training is a type of education aimed at teaching and educating children, developing them intellectually, spiritually and morally, aesthetically and physically, as well as preparing children for general secondary education.

- It is stated that "pre-school education-upbringing" means one-year preparation of children aged six to seven years for primary education.

Comprehensive development of a child in preschool education is the basis for significant achievements in general education. The early development of a child is of decisive importance in his future formation as a person.

Materials and Methods

The stage of preschool education is the most important and responsible stage of continuous education, where the foundations and foundations of child upbringing and education are formed. The main tasks of preschool education are to educate children in the spirit of the nation's rich national, cultural, historical heritage and spiritual and moral traditions, to form children's feelings of national patriotism, to form the need for education in children of preschool age, and to develop their inclination to study regular preparation for the educational process, development of children's thinking, formation of skills of independent and free expression of one's opinion, provision of physical and mental health of children.

At this stage, the issue of preparing children for school education is one of the most pressing issues. With this in mind, today fundamental changes are being made in the field of preschool education in our country, in the field of preparing children for school education. In the field of preschool education, President Sh.M. The works being carried out on Mirziyoyev's active initiative, decrees and decisions are gaining importance. Establishment of the Ministry of Pre-School Education, the President's Resolution No. 2707 (29 December 2016) "On Measures to Further Improve the Pre-School Education System in 2017-2021", "Pre-school Education Decree No. PF-5198 (September 30, 2017) "On measures to fundamentally improve the management of the education system", Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the activities of preschool educational institutions" Decision No. 528 (July 19, 2017), the adoption of official documents such as the "Concept for developing the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" is a special step in improving the quality and efficiency of education in the preschool education system. rin is taking over.

Stages of child development and preparation for school education. Children of pre-school education age are mainly prepared for school education in pre-school education organizations and in the family. Development of children in preschool educational organizations and preparation for school education is carried out in 3 stages.

1. Development of children's speech.
2. Physical development.
3. Development of meaning.

The state requirements for the education of children of preschool age are to form them in a healthy and mature way, prepared for school and study.

The concept of the child's readiness for school education. According to the Regulation on preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a child can receive preschool education at home, through independent education by parents, or in permanent preschool educational organizations, as well as preschool educational organizations. Preschool education for underprivileged children takes place in organizations, schools, special groups or centers organized in neighborhoods. Here they practice 2-3 times a week.

Parents are given the right to choose the form of preschool education. When determining the readiness of a 6-7-year-old child for school education, the primary condition for preschool education is that the child's readiness for school serves as a bridge for the lifestyle and activities of the preschool and school period, family or preschool education. they should take into account the need to ensure a smooth transition to school education in the educational conditions of the organization. Admission of a preschool child to school education always brings about serious changes in his life, morals, interests and relationships. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare the child for home school education, to familiarize him with not so difficult knowledge, concepts, skills and abilities. According to leading experts, the concept of "Preparation for School" includes the following areas of preparing a child for school:

- ethical;
- mental;
- physical;

Moral and voluntary readiness of the child to study at school.

Ethical-volitional readiness to study at school allows the child to actively acquire a new social point of view in the development of moral behavior, will, moral emotions and consciousness by the end of preschool childhood, and to build interactions with his teacher and classmates on a moral basis. is expressed in reaching the level that gives. Moral volitional readiness is manifested at a certain level of the development of the personal behavior of a child of preschool age. In this regard, the child's ability to manage his own behavior, which develops during the preschool education age: to consciously follow the

rules or the teacher's requirements, not to allow himself to get nervous suddenly, to show determination in achieving the set goal, to do the necessary work for himself the ability to perform, as opposed to distracting from the goal, etc. deserve attention. Moral-volitional readiness for school, as well as moral feeling and child it is also expressed by a certain level of consciousness development. The most exemplary thing here is to understand the social importance of children's moral behavior, to develop in them the ability to independently evaluate their behavior, to form the elements of responsibility, honesty, humanity and civic feelings.

Moral and voluntary readiness includes a set of qualities that express the attitude of a child of preschool age to work. This is the desire to work, respect for the work of others, and the acquisition of necessary labor skills.

Mental readiness of the child to study at school. An important component of mental readiness for school is the presence of a sufficiently broad wealth of knowledge about the environment and the world in a child entering school. This fund of knowledge is the necessary basis on which the teacher relies in organizing his work. The quality of knowledge acquired by children is important for the mental readiness of the child for school. The indicator of the quality of knowledge is, first of all, the fact that they are consciously acquired by children; clear and differentiated imagination; completeness of content and volume of simple concepts; ability to independently apply knowledge in solving educational and practical tasks that are understandable to them; regularity, that is, the ability of preschoolers to reflect understandable, important connections and relationships between things and events.

A component of a child's mental preparation for school is a certain level of cognitive development. First, the growing voluntariness of the cognitive process; the ability to voluntarily remember and repeat the material in terms of meaning, to perceive things and events in a planned way, to know what is set and to solve practical problems according to the purpose, and so on; secondly, to increase the quality of cognitive processes, the accuracy of sensations, the completeness and differentiation of perception, the speed and accuracy of recollection and repetition; thirdly, it is important that the child has a relationship with the environment, the desire to acquire knowledge and study at school. The general level of mental activity of the future student is important in the formation of mental readiness for school. The ability to multi-faceted analysis of things in children's thinking activities in the regular, purposeful working conditions of MTT related to the mental education of children, the ability to use sensory standards of social composition in researching the characteristics and qualities of science and events, the main connection and dependence of things and events, the ability to make simple generalizations based on the identification of signs, the ability to compare things based on the consistent separation of similar and different signs is included.

Elementary independence of mental activity, the ability to independently plan one's practical activity and implement it based on a plan, the ability to set a simple knowledge task and solve it, and so on, will be developed in future students. Mental readiness at school also includes the acquisition of elements of educational activities by children. Thus, mental readiness to study at school consists of interconnected components of mental and speech development of children. The unity of cognitive activity, cognitive interests, children's ways of thinking, conscious systematized ideas about the surrounding world and elemental ideas, speech and the general level of elementary educational activity creates mental readiness in children to master the educational material at school.

Physical readiness of the child to study at school.

The physical readiness of the child to study at school is of great importance for the success of the study. In connection with going to school, the reconstruction of the child's lifestyle, change of the daily routine, serious academic work, the duration of classes require significant physical effort. Physical readiness for school consists of many components. This

is, first of all, the good health of the child, the fitness of the body, a certain level of endurance and work ability, and the ability to resist diseases. The development of small finger muscles takes a special place in preparing children for school, which is a necessary condition for successful writing. Physical readiness for school also implies the acquisition of cultural hygiene skills by the child, the cultivation of the habit of observing the rules of personal hygiene. Physical fitness is a necessary component of a child's readiness for school.

In determining readiness for school, the assessment of the state of the child's health and the biological maturity of the organism (anthropometric indicators, bone, muscle, respiratory and cardiovascular system) is based on a multifactorial analysis that assumes the development of functional readiness for school, "Maturity for School" indicator and, above all, it is used to evaluate the level of development of a number of physiological functions. These include: the development of the ability to brake, which is necessary for sitting at a desk for a long time; good control of movements, including the fine movements of the fingers necessary to perform graphic tasks related to writing and drawing; relatively fast formation and strengthening of positive and inhibitory conditional connections, as well as sufficient development of the second signal system.

Conclusion

By the end of preschool childhood in regular educational conditions, children are able to master the main components of educational activities: to accept an understandable educational task, to understand and accurately follow the teacher's instructions, to achieve a result by doing the work using the methods shown by adults, or they should acquire the ability to control their activity, behavior, the quality of task performance, and the ability to critically assess their own and other children's work.

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